

The Effect of Halogen Substituents on the U.V. Spectra of Some Aza-Aromatics

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The effect of halogen substituents on the U. V. spectra of alternant hydrocarbons has been discussed by Peters¹. As the inductive effect of a substituent, represented by the change in coulomb integral of the carbon atom to which it is attached, has little or no effect on the energy of $N \rightarrow V_1$ transition of alternant hydrocarbons, only the conjugative effect was considered. However, the inductive effect of a substituent plays an important role in deciding the magnitude as well as the direction on the shifts in the longest wave length ($N \rightarrow V_1$) band of aza-aromatics. In the present work we have, therefore, considered both the inductive and conjugative effects.

The principles of the method, based on Longuet-Higgins and Sowden² perturbation technique, originally employed for methyl substitution, are as follows:

Inductive Effect.—When a ring hydrogen atom is replaced by a halogen atom the coulomb integral of the halogenated carbon atom is altered, owing to the inductive effect of the halogen atom. If 'a' and 'b' refer to the highest filled and lowest empty molecular orbitals respectively, the net change in the transition energy due to the inductive effect is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} (\Delta E_{ba})_{\text{inductive}} &= (E'_b - E'_a) - (E_b - E_a) \\ &= (C'_{br} - C_{ar})\delta \alpha_r + \left(\sum_{j \neq b} \frac{C'_{br} C_{jr}}{E_b - E_j} - \sum_{j \neq a} \frac{C_{ar} C_{jr}}{E_a - E_j} \right) (\delta \alpha_r^2) \dots \quad (A) \end{aligned}$$

Where the primed quantities refer to the halogenated aza-aromatics carrying the halogen atom at the r th carbon atom and the unprimed to the parent compound. C_{jr} refers to atomic orbital coefficients of the r th carbon atom in the j th molecular orbital, and $\delta \alpha_r$ is the change in the coulomb integral of the r th carbon atom.

Conjugative Effect.—The conjugative effect is dealt with by supposing that the result of the addition of a single p-orbital of coulomb integral F_a , to the molecular orbitals of the parent compound, is a perturbation of the latter orbitals. The resulting change in the energy of the $N \rightarrow V_1$ transitions is given by:³

$$(\Delta E_{ba})_{\text{conjugative}} = \left(\frac{C'_{br}}{E_b - E_a} - \frac{C_{ar}}{E_a - E_a} \right) \beta^2_{rs} \dots \quad (B)$$

1. D. Peters, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1957, 1993.

2. H. C. Longuet-Higgins and R. G. Sowden, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 1404.

where β_{rs} is the resonance integral of the bond formed between the r th carbon atom of the parent compound and the halogen atom.

The resultant effect of the substituent is obtained by adding the two separate effects and the effect of two or more halogen atoms has been considered additive. In equations (A) and (B) there are three quantities which must be assigned for each substituent, the coulomb integral E_s , the resonance integral β_{rs} and the inductive parameter $\delta \alpha_r$. The values chosen for these quantities are set out in Table I.

TABLE I

Substituent	F.	Cl.	Br.
E_s	$\alpha + 2.5\beta$	$\alpha + 1.5\beta$	$\alpha + 1.3\beta$
β_{rs}	0.7β	0.45β	0.35β
$\delta \alpha_r$	$+0.15\beta$	0.1β	$+0.07\beta$

α and β refer to the coulomb and resonance integrals of carbon atom and C=C bond of benzene respectively.

The choice of the coulomb integral is based on the order of the electronegativities and the values of $\delta \alpha_r$ have been taken roughly equal to one sixteenth of the difference between E_s and α . The choice of parameter is amply justified by reasonable agreement between calculated and observed spectral shifts.

The molecular orbital energies and the atomic orbital coefficients for all the compounds have been taken from Coulson and Streitwieser³ with $\alpha_M = \alpha + 0.5\beta$ and $\beta_{oM} = \beta$, unless otherwise stated.

The results are set out in table II, where the column headed by $\Delta\lambda$ is the energy difference converted into wavelength ($m\mu$) calculated by taking $\beta = -23000 \text{ cm}^{-1}$.

DISCUSSION

In collecting the observed spectral data given in the Table II for a comparison with the calculated shifts, the results of measurements made under comparable conditions have been chosen as far as possible. In the case of pyridine, where comparable data were available only in acid medium, the calculations were repeated with the following parameters:— $\alpha_M = \alpha + 0.86\beta$ and α_0 (carbon attached to the nitrogen atom) = $\alpha + 0.9825\beta$. The values of the spectral shifts calculated with those parameters, are given in parenthesis. The improved agreement between the calculated and experimental results is obvious. However, the overall agreement, in general, is satisfactory except in the case of dichloro-derivatives of pyrazine where the calculated shifts are too high. Whether this poor agreement is due to the failure of additivity approximation made in the calculation or otherwise, cannot be ascertained as data for mono-chloro derivative were not available. Although in the case of pyrimidine and pyridazine additivity approximation appears to be satisfactory.

3. G. A. Coulson and A. Streitwieser, "Dictionary of π -electron calculations". (Pergamon Press, London) 1965, 246, 254, 257.

TABLE II

Compound	Calculated $\Delta\lambda(\text{m}\mu)$	Observed $\Delta\lambda(\text{m}\mu)$	Reference
PYRIDINE			
2-chloro—	10.5 (12.4)	14	4a
3-chloro—	11.2 (11.5)	14	"
4-chloro—	0.6(0.4)	2	4d
2-bromo—	11.6 (14.8)	16	4a
3-bromo—	11.6 (13.6)	18	"
4-bromo—	0.6 (0.4)	—	—
2-fluoro—	0.6 (6.4)	4	4a
3-fluoro—	6.6 (5.8)	6	"
4-fluoro—	≈ 0 (≈ 0)	—	—
PYRIMIDINE			
2-chloro—	12.0	9	4b
5-chloro—	20.3	18	"
6-chloro—	6.2	4	"
2-bromo—	15.4	—	—
5-bromo—	26.3	23	4b
6-bromo—	13.3	—	—
4,6-dichloro—	12.7	11	4b
2,4-dichloro—	18.8	15	"
2,5-dichloro—	34.5	29	"
2,4,6-trichloro—	26.0	20	4b
2,4,5-trichloro—	42.7	30	4b
PYRIDAZINE			
3, chloro—	14.6	14	4b
4-chloro—	3.6	—	—
3,6-dichloro—	31.2	32	4c
3,4,5-trichloro—	23.1	20	"
3,4,6-trichloro—	35.9	30	"
3,4,5,6, tetrachloro—	40.8	33	"
PYRAZINE			
mono-chloro—	12.4	—	—
mono-bromo—	13.8	13	4c
mono-fluoro—	7.3	—	—
2,3-dichloro—	26.2	17	4d
2,5-dichloro—	26.2	12	"
2,6-dichloro—	26.2	12	"
2,6-dibromo—	29.3	25	"
Tribromo—	42.6	47	"

The present calculation shows that the conjugative effect may be hypsochromic or bathochromic depending on the positions of the substituent unlike alternant hydrocarbons where it is always bathochromic. The resultant bathochromic shift in all the cases

4a. H. C. Brown and D. H. McDaniel, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 3752.

4b. (Mis) M. P. V. Boarland and J. F. W. McComie, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, 3716, 3722.

4c. Von. K. Eichenberger, R. Rometsch and J. Druey, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1954, 37, 1298.

4d. J. P. Phillips and F. C. Nachod, "Organic Electronic Spectral Data" (Interscience Publishers London) 1963, 4, pp. 12, 27.

4e. M. J. Kamlet, "Organic Electronic Spectral Data" (Interscience Publishers, New York) 1960 1, pp. 16, 17.

examined is due to the fact that whenever the conjugative effect is hypsochromic the inductive effect is bathochromic.

In some cases the two effects may almost neutralise each other resulting in a very small shift as, indeed, is the case with 4-halo substituted pyridines.

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